

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359845221>

MyoHome: A Smart Home System integrating Augmented Reality with Natural Interfaces based on Hand Gestures

Chapter · September 2021

CITATIONS

0

READS

112

2 authors:

Oscar Osorio Giraldez
University of Granada

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Juan A. Holgado-Terriza
University of Granada

148 PUBLICATIONS 2,150 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

MyoHome: A Smart Home System integrating Augmented Reality with Natural Interfaces based on Hand Gestures.

Oscar Osorio Giraldez
Software Engineering Department
University of Granada
oog@ugr.es

Juan Antonio Holgado Terriza
Software Engineering Department
University of Granada
jholgado@ugr.es

ABSTRACT

A novel smart home automation system was developed for controlling home devices integrating augmented reality (AR) with natural human-computer interface based on hand gestures. This paper resumes the main issues required for its implementation.

KEYWORDS

Smart, home, automation, gestures, AR, extended, augmented, reality, devices, Android, Unity, Vuforia, Assistant, house, raspberry, NUI, natural, human-computer interface.

1 Introduction

The novel natural interaction systems such as gesture control or voice assistant afford recent advances to human-computer interfaces (HCI). In conjunction with augmented reality (AR) they can provide an accurate and rich visualization of the environment controlled in a more natural and effective way by natural interfaces.

This work presents an innovative home automation system based on recent natural interfaces in combination with augmented reality. On one hand, AR includes virtual 3D model to the environment which allows to know the status of home devices available in the home, while the natural interface based on hand gesture enables the control of these home devices.

In this brief summary, a description of the system is presented as well as the main issues, technologies and techniques to be considered for the development of the initial prototype. Finally, the main conclusions and the future works to improve the system are presented.

2 MYO-HOME System

Myo Home is basically an innovative smart home automation system controlled by a hand gesture HCI interface that allow the control of home devices. These home devices can be bulbs, locks, plugs, TV, thermostats or any other physical device accessible by an internet connection, that is, smart devices based on Internet of things (IoT). In the system, these devices are represented by 3D models generated by computer that can be visualized on top of real-world image targets by the application of AR techniques when the user orients his/her camera to image targets. Figure 1 shows a typical scenario for the MYO Home operation.

Figure 1: Representation of the system scenario

2.1 System Architecture

MYO Home has a client-server multilayer architecture composed by four layers: the perception layer, processing layer, control layer, and finally the device layer, as it is shown in Figure 2.

In the **perception layer** the status of home devices is perceived visually by AR and the hand gestures carried out for controlling home devices by a gestural interface. For the perception of the gestural interaction, a device is used to capture the electromyographic (EMG) signals of the hand gestures realized by the user, which are subsequently identified in the processing layer.

For a visual perception of home devices we use a camera oriented to image target in order to visualize the status of generated 3D virtual devices.

In the **processing layer**, the captured gestures are identified and interpreted on the one hand to apply the corresponding actions on selected home device. To do that, the actions to be executed to home devices are transmitted to home gateway in the control layer. On the other hand, the virtual elements generated for each home device are processed and generated by AR into the capture camera images at real-time. The processing layer is deployed on a mobile device such as a smartphone.

Figure 2: Architecture of the system.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons
"Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International" license.

In the **control layer**, the home gateway is responsible to receive the actions to be applied on home devices from the processing layer and, then, the corresponding actions are sent to specific home devices using a home communication protocol such as Bluetooth or Wifi.

Finally, the **device layer** contains the set of individual IoT home devices integrated into the system that are accessible through a local network.

2.2 Implementation

Next, the main hardware devices and software infrastructures selected for the development of the system is discussed.

In the **processing layer** an Android smartphone was chosen for the implementation for several reasons. First, the device contains an integrated camera that can be used for real-world image capture and a screen to visualize digital 3D models of home devices on top of image targets. This allow us to implement the software controller for processing AR models in the same device used for capturing images; this is an ideal workbench for the implementation and test of the system. In addition, the smartphone is responsible of receiving the status of home devices updating the visualization of generated 3D models as well as the identification of gestures when the user interacts with the system enabling new actions over home devices.

The main application in Android smartphone was implemented using the Unity3D game engine in order to simplify the creation and the generation of virtual 3D models as well as their dynamic and rendering. The AR was implemented by the integration of Vuforia engine into Unity. Vuforia makes available the mechanisms for positioning the 3D model over the real-world image target. During the development of the project, the capabilities of Unity on one hand and Vuforia on the other hand were studied and investigated in order to improve the AR performance with respect to the detection and tracking of image targets, the visualization of 3D models, the response time to user actions or status changes of home devices, among others. The logic of the application and 3D models was implemented in C# language programming using Visual Studio (and its extensions). The visual styles of the application and the scenario were designed with Unity, implementing the 2D interface and the scene by positioning 3D models and different lights and cameras. On the other hand, a set of icons were designed by searching, testing and editing different icon families aided by Photoshop and Illustrator in order to integrate them inside the developed interface. These tools allow also to create the logo of the Myo Home system.

All the code development has been guided by the use of good software engineering practices.

In the **perception layer** the camera of the smartphone was used for visual perception. After analyzing some commercial devices, the Myo Armband was selected, consisting of a bracelet with EMG sensors, and a Bluetooth connection to transmit the electromyographic signals to a mobile phone in the processing layer. We have studied the official SDK of Myo Armband manufacturer in order to find the best way to modify and adapt it to facilitate the integration with Unity through an external plugin developed by Florian Strieg on Github (<https://github.com/f->

[strieg/MyoUnityAndroidPlugin](https://github.com/f-strieg/MyoUnityAndroidPlugin)). We have developed the menus and controls necessary for integration and connection through the app. A consistent, intuitive, natural, and universal gesture language has been studied, developed and implemented in the Unity application using the gesture vocabulary available in the plugin

Figure 3: Gestures and meanings of each one.

In the **control layer** a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B device was used to interconnect the smart home devices with the main application (smartphone) through the local network. The device runs Home Assistant platform as a gateway for the control and integration of all home automation devices in a centralized manner. A complete configuration and deployment of each home device were carried out before they are linked to the gateway. YAML scripts were implemented to configure each home device as well as the insertion of some REST services.

The **smart devices layer** has been implemented and tested with a smart plug and a smart IR receiver/emitter device for control a TV and an air conditioning unit through infrared communication. YAML scripts were implemented for recording IR commands used by TV set and air conditioning unit from a standard IR remote control. The IR commands are then stored in the gateway in order to reproduce the IR commands addressed by smartphone in processing layer when the user executes the hand gesture that corresponds to the specific command.

Figure 4: Myo Home in use

3 Conclusions and Future Work

A complete prototype of the Myo Home system was developed and tested in this work. Some preliminary results show that the response time of the system is very good, although more deep tests with users have to be performed.

Some of the improvements to be done to the initial prototype as a future works should be the implementation of new configurations for helping the addition of new devices from the app; improving gesture language increasing the gesture vocabulary; improving the battery consumption; the applied AR algorithms and finally the interaction ergonomics and usability by using AR glasses.